

Group Teaching for Hispanic Women with Metabolic Syndrome

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Background

Metabolic Syndrome is the presence of at least three cardiovascular risk indicators.

- Diabetes or insulin resistance
- Hypertension
- Central obesity
- Dyslipidemia
- Risk indicator treatment

Origin

- Physical inactivity & Dietary
- Heredity

Complications

- Diabetes Type II
- CVD, Heart attack, & Stroke
- Dementia
- Cancer & PCOS

Population

Under and uninsured Hispanic women aged 40-64 years old of Indio and Coachella Valley receiving primary care at Volunteers in Medicine, a free community clinic.

Statement of the Problem

- Hispanic women are a diverse cultural group
- Among the fastest growing group affected
 - Limited health literacy
 - Family needs precede self, including health
 - Believe that they are powerless to improve wellness

Purpose

To develop and pilot a group educational program for Hispanic women between the ages of 40-64 years old with and at risk for metabolic syndrome to empower, improve lifestyle choices, and positively affect quality of life.

Health Promotion Model

- Guide to motive individuals
- Empower patients
- Requires deliberate patient action
- Holistic approach

Adapted from Nola Pender's Health Promotion Model

Educational Plan

Intervention Phase I

Verbal instruction: Description of metabolic syndrome and health significance

Intervention Phase II

Physical activity: Activity needs, time requirements.
Certified Group fitness instructor: Demonstration of body weight and stretching exercises

Intervention Phase III

Nutrition: Facts and requirements. Healthy food alternatives, and high alert foods.

Methods

Setting: Volunteers in Medicine

Sample: Hispanic women 40-64 yo with and at risk for metabolic syndrome

Intervention: 3 Phase group teaching course

Risks: Fatigue

Benefits: Increased knowledge, self efficacy, confidence, and health. \$10 Target gift card, yoga mat, activity log, calendar and stickers for all participants.

Evaluation

Evaluation of the educator and intervention

- Participant completion of pre-post test
- Participant verbal affirmation of content understanding

Data

Data Analysis

- Paired samples t-test
- Post hoc analysis

Results

Paired samples t-test

Clinically insignificant findings

Post hoc analysis

- Small sample & large effect size
- 28 participants needed

Ceiling effect observed

- Question simplicity
- Preexisting knowledge

Anecdotal participant perception

- Increased understanding
- Increase sense of empowerment

Implications

Cultural Implications

- Understanding population needs
- Foster individual health knowledge and accountability

Provider Implications

- Development and refinement of effective tools to reach middle aged Hispanic women
- Patient-provider relationship development
- Foster increased peer support and enthusiasm